

The Impact of Implementing the Regional Development Information System (SIPD) on the Effectiveness of Village Organizations Through Employee Performance in the Malang City Government

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Abstract:- The main objective of this research is to analyze and explain the effect of implementing a Management Information System, namely the Regional Development Information System (SIPD), on the Effectiveness of Subdistrict Organizations in the Malang City Government through Employee Performance. This research includes quantitative research. The sampling technique used saturated sampling (sample determination when all members are used) with a total of 57 respondents. The data collection method uses a questionnaire, data analysis uses descriptive statistics and inferential statistics, namely path analysis. The results of this research found that the Regional Development Information System influences employee performance, the regional development information system influences organizational effectiveness, employee performance influences organizational effectiveness, the regional development information system influences organizational effectiveness through employee performance. So from the results of this research it was found that the existence of a regional development information system can improve the performance of sub-district employees in the Malang City Government, and also have an impact on the effectiveness of organizations in the Malang City Government. From this research it can be concluded that the existence of a development information system can make the work of sub-district secretaries younger so that there is effectiveness and efficiency in existing work and responsibilities

Keywords:- Regional Development Information System (SIPD), Employee Performance, Organizational Effectiveness.

I. INTRODUCTION

Regional development planning is a process of preparing activity stages that involve various stakeholder elements, utilizing and allocating existing resources, as well as improving the social welfare of a regional environment within a certain period of time. Stakeholders involved in regional development planning can be classified into 3 domains, namely government institutions which include the regional executive and legislature, the private sector which can be categorized as business actors, both individuals and

institutions, and the community, both individuals and groups. In the planning process, efforts need to be made that have a focus point to achieve a condition of balance in the context of problem solving, future orientation and resource allocation (Mawardi et al., 2023)

An application-based integrated government information system, where the progress of information technology development has reached the level of being a necessity in various aspects of people's lives. The behavior and activities of society and organizations depend a lot on information technology so that effectiveness and efficiency are the main considerations in improving organizational performance, both in companies and the government. A management information system is a collection of interconnected components that collect (or obtain), process, store and distribute information to support decision making and monitoring within an organization (Effendy et al., 2021)(Agustina et al., 2021). A job has certain requirements to be able to be carried out in achieving goals which are also known as work standards. Performance is the result of the work performance that an employee has achieved in accordance with his/her job function in a certain period. (Shodiq et al., 2018). (Widiawati et al., 2021) Individual performance can be measured by several indicators, namely quality, quantity, time, cost, unsupervised ability and individual behavior.

Since 2020 the central government has implemented the Regional Development Information System (SIPD) which is also contained in Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 70 of 2019 concerning Regional Development Information Systems which is an amendment to Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 98 of 2018 concerning Regional Development Information Systems and must be implemented by each local government. This SIPD application has been integrated with the design and budgeting menu so that control and supervision activities can be carried out directly at the same time. Another advantage is that this input system can be carried out by the section head of each activity as an operator in accordance with the regulations that the section head is also the person in charge of the activity or the technical implementing officer for the activity(Rachmawati et al., 2020)(Muizah et al., 2021). This application will certainly be able to ease the

work previously carried out by one operator for one agency where errors due to human error were very large due to the large workload with a large level of risk. The implementation of the Regional Development Information System aims to improve organizational (agency) performance in achieving performance targets in accordance with predetermined benchmarks. The Regional Development Information System will run optimally if it is carried out by employees as operators who have abilities and skills in the computer field. Everything related to improving employee performance should be the attention of every element of organizational leadership, therefore employee ability is the main capital for achieving the goals or targets of an organization. All matters related to improving employee performance should be the attention of every element of leadership in order to achieve the success of the agency(Hidayatullah et al., 2020)(Y. A. D. Pratama et al., 2021)(Y. A. D. Pratama et al., 2021)

In the sub-district secretariat, which is held by the sub-district secretary as the main task bearer of planning, budgeting and implementing office activities, the use of the SIPD application is of course highly expected to support the success of the sub-district (organization) performance in achieving predetermined targets more effectively and efficiently. Based on the performance achievements of regional apparatus, namely the community satisfaction index and the percentage of planning, financial and reporting documents, researchers need to test the effect of implementing the Regional Development Information System on the effectiveness of sub-district organizations in the Malang City Regional Government through employee performance. From the previous background description, the problem formulation can be drawn, namely (Nurhanifah et al., 2023)(Nasir et al., 2022) (Suhendra, 2021); 1) What is the description of the regional development information system, the effectiveness of sub-district organizations and employee performance in the Malang City Government? 2) how does the regional development information system (SIPD) influence the effectiveness of sub-district organizations in the Malang City Government? 3) How does the regional development information system influence the performance of sub-district employees in the Malang City Government? 4) How does employee performance influence the effectiveness of sub-district organizations in the Malang City Government? 5) How does the regional development information system influence organizational effectiveness through the performance of sub-district employees in the Malang City Government?

II. EASE OF USE

A. Regional Development Information System

An information system is a system consisting of all components that work together to process data and produce information(Ari Purnomo et al., 2022). Another opinion was expressed by (S. Alvianna & Hidayatullah, 2020)(Aso et al., 2021) that management information systems are very dependent on components in producing information systems that suit their needs. Gaps that occur in the implementation of these components will result in information that is less accurate, less detailed, less timely and less relevant which results in errors in decision making in companies or organizations.

B. Employee Performance

Employee Performance according to (Paais & Pattiruhu, 2020)(Zhenjing et al., 2022) Effectiveness means that a particular program can be achieved precisely according to plan, work is carried out in accordance with predetermined work procedures, management resources are available completely and precisely as needed to achieve goals, various management resources can be used appropriately and organizational goals are achieved according to plan. which has been specified. Then obey (Wolor et al., 2022)(Masduki Asbari et al., 2021)Work effectiveness can be seen from 3 aspects, namely: accuracy of quality, accuracy of quantity and timeliness. From this opinion, work effectiveness is not only a result that can be seen from 3 aspects, namely: accuracy of quality, accuracy of quantity and timeliness. From this opinion, work effectiveness is not only a result achieved in a certain period of time using various organizational components but also efficiency because these three aspects must be achieved simultaneously.

C. Organizational Effectiveness

Organizational Effectiveness acc (Dhoopar et al., 2023)(Titus & Hoole, 2021) The success of an organization really depends on management's ability to integrate all the elements within it starting from human resources, systems, organizational structure, technology, organizational culture and the environment so that it has the ability to adapt to changes that occur in its internal environment or the pressure that comes. from external. Another opinion expressed by (Meilani et al., 2021) (Laub, 1999)states that organizational effectiveness is the concept of how effective an organization is in achieving the results desired by the organization.

Fig. 1: Organizational Effectiveness

III. PREPARE YOUR PAPER BEFORE STYLING

This research focuses on the study of management information systems, especially those related to management information systems, especially those related to Regional Development Information Systems, employee performance, and organizational effectiveness. This research focuses on the study of information systems management, especially explanatory research (Ari Purnomo et al., 2022) (Drigas et al., 2020) Explanatory research is research that analyzes the influence of one variable on another variable, and also

explains the position of each variable studied, with research locations carried out in all sub-districts within Malang City government agencies. The population in this study were all subdistrict secretaries in Malang City, totaling 57 employees. As for the sample of this research, in my opinion (Pakpahan et al., 2022)(Stephanie et al., 2019) that saturated sampling is a sampling technique when all members of the population are used as samples. Data analysis techniques use descriptive statistical analysis, structural equation model test analysis, classical assumption testing and hypothesis testing.

Table 1: Operational Definition

No	Research Variable	Operational Definition	Indicator
1.	Regional Development Information System (X)	This Regional Development Information System (SIPD) is a development of the previous application but only has one function, namely planning. SIPD is designed to produce information that can be used by management to make appropriate decisions and in accordance with the rules and can be supervised and controlled by internal audit such as the inspectorate in an up-to-date manner.	X.1 System Quality X.2 Information Quality X.3 Use
2.	Employee Performance (Y1)	The employee whose main duties and functions are in charge of planning, budgeting and finance in the sub-district is the sub-district secretary. The employee performance variable measures the impact of using regional development information system (SIPD) applications in improving performance.	Y.1.1 Knowledge Y.1.2 Ability Y.1.3 Skill
3.	Organizational Effectiveness (Y2)	perception of the achievement of the work program that has been set. Organizational effectiveness is the level of success in achieving the goals and targets that have been set down in the work program during one period.	Y.2.1 Productivity Y.2.2 Service Quality Y.2.3 Responsiveness Y.2.4 Accountability

IV. USING THE TEMPLATE

Of the 5 sub-districts under the Malang City Government, there are 57 sub-districts under the Malang City government. The results of the hypothesis analysis for each path obtained from the path results using SPSS software are as follows:

A. Demographic Statistic

Table 2: Demographic Profil

Item	Optional	Frequency	percentag
Gender	Male	57	100
	Female	0	0
Age	35 - 40 years	17	29,82
	> 40 - 45 t years	11	19,30
	> 45 - 50 years	16	28,07
	> 50 - 55 years	8	14,04
	> 55 years	5	8,77
Lama Kerja	6 - 10 years	7	12,28
	11 - 15 years	21	36,84
	16 - 20 years	17	29,83
	>20 years	12	21,05
Pendidikan	Diploma	0	0
	Bachelor Degree	45	78,95
	Master Degree	12	21,05

Model 1 Analysis
Model 1 Equation $Y1= X+e1$

Table 3: Model 1 Analysis Test Results

Independent Variable	Regression Coefficients	T Count	Sig
Regional Development Information System	0,691	7,086	0,000
Variabel Dependent	Employee Performance		
R	0,691		
R square (R ²)	0,477		
Adj. R square	0,468		
F	50,205		
Sig	0,000		

Model 2 Analysis

Model 2 Equation $Y_2 = X + Y_1 + e_2$

Table 4: Model 2 Analysis Test Results

Independent Variable	Regression Coefficients	T Count	Sig
Regional Development Information System	0,453	3,619	0,001
Employee Performance	0,357	2,849	0,006
Variabel Dependent	Organizational Effectiveness		
R	0,746		
R square (R ²)	0,557		
Adj. R square	0,540		
F	33,918		
Sig	0,000		

Referring to the test results of model 2, it can be seen that the significant value of the Regional Development Information System variable (X) = 0.001, and employee performance (Y1) = 0.006 is smaller than 0.05. This provides the conclusion that the Regional Development Information System variable (X) and employee performance variables have a significant effect on organizational effectiveness. Regional Development Information Systems (X) and employee performance (Y1) influence the organizational effectiveness variable (Y2). The value of R² or Rsquare in the model summary table is 0.557, this shows

that the contribution or influence of X and Y1 on Y2 is 55.7%, while the remaining 44.3% is the contribution of other variables. not included in the study. Meanwhile the value of $el = \sqrt{(1-0.557)} = \sqrt{(0.443)} = 0.665$

To find out whether the regression model II above has a joint or simultaneous influence, an F test is needed. The F test shows that the output of the regression model II results is an F count of 33.918 with a significant value of 0.000, this means $0.000 < 0.05$, this means X and Y1 together have a significant effect on Y2.

B. Uji Hipotesis

Table 5: Calculation of direct, indirect and total effects

Hypothesis	Direct Effect	Sig	Indirect Effect	Total Effect	Keterangan
X → Y1	0.691	0.000	-	-	Signifikan
X → Y2	0.453	0.000	-	-	Signifikan
Y1 → Y2	0.357	0.000	-	-	Signifikan
X → Y1 → Y2		-	$0.691 \times 0.357 = 0.246$	$0.246 + 0.453 = 0.699$	Moderasi Parsial

Based on the test results in the table... it is known that the coefficient of the Regional Development Information System, employee performance, and organizational effectiveness, all variables are known to have a significant effect on organizational effectiveness. The probability value of each variable is 0.000. Meanwhile, the indirect influence of the Regional Development Information System variable on organizational effectiveness through employee performance obtained significant results.

V. DISCUSSION

- The Influence of Regional Development Information Systems on Employee Performance. From testing using the SPSS program, the regression results show that the influence of the Regional Development Information System on employee performance, variable) can be interpreted as the first hypothesis which states that there is an influence between the Regional Development

Information System on employee performance and can be accepted or tested statistically. The results of this research are in line with research conducted by (Sharma & Taneja, 2018) (Rondonuwu et al., 2022) that a management information system can run if it has system quality and information quality that supports it so that someone wants to use the information system, another opinion was expressed by (Gunawan & Hidayatullah, 2023) (Lasarudin et al., 2022) When the information system runs well, users will use it by increasing loyalty and faithfulness to the goods/services

- The Influence of Regional Development Information Systems on Organizational Effectiveness. From testing using the SPSS program, the results of the second model (II) regression show the influence of the Regional Development Information System on organizational effectiveness, variable $F(0.05)$ can be interpreted as an influence between the Regional Development Information System on organizational effectiveness that can be accepted or tested statistically. The results of this research are in line with research conducted by (Adi et al., 2022) (B. P. Pratama et al., 2021) said that management information systems can support smart cities in Batu City by optimizing information and communication technology together. Another opinion was expressed that every organization must have a different work environment, including job diversity which is designed to increase organizational effectiveness (Reetu et al., 2022) (Yadav et al., 2022) (Hidayatullah et al., 2023), Likewise, the existence of a management information system at the sub-district level of Malang City Government is expected to help organizational effectiveness.
- The Influence of Employee Performance on Organizational Effectiveness. From testing using the SPSS program, the results of the second model (II) regression show the influence of employee performance on organizational effectiveness, variable F_1 (employee performance) obtained a calculated t value = 2.849 with a significant level of 0.006, meaning that using alpha (significant limit) 5% (0, 05) can be interpreted as the influence of employee performance on organizational effectiveness that can be accepted or tested statistically. This article is in line with research conducted by (McCarter et al., 2022) (Singh et al., 2019) (Estikowati et al., 2022) said that work motivation and the work environment also have an influence on employee performance, so that not only rewards can improve employee performance but several other factors also influence it. Other opinions were also expressed regarding factors that can influence organizational effectiveness, one of which is motivation (Irawan, Maarif, & Affandi, 2015), (Yakup, 2017) says that organizational culture, work motivation will influence employee job satisfaction, employee job satisfaction will have an impact on increasing or decreasing employee performance which, if it occurs in the long term, will also have an impact on organizational effectiveness.
- The Influence of Regional Development Information Systems on Organizational Effectiveness through Employee Performance. Employee performance as a

moderating variable between the Regional Development Information System and organizational effectiveness can be seen from the magnitude of the indirect effect (indirect effect) with a direct effect with a value of ($0.453 > 0.246$) that exists from the Regional Development Information System on employee performance on effectiveness of local government organizations in Malang City. So it can be concluded that this research is in line with research conducted by (Donkor, 2021) (Wang et al., 2022) (Lasarudin et al., 2022) Management information systems not only make things easier for employees and increase organizational effectiveness but can also facilitate learning, therefore there is a need to improve the quality of information (Stella Alvianna et al., 2020) (Hidayatullah et al., 2022), another opinion expressed by (Ratnasari, 2017) that in order to improve employee performance and optimize organizational effectiveness, it is necessary to carry out employee work evaluations in order to find out how effective the existing Regional Development Information System is with the optimal role of sub-district organizations in the Malang City government environment. The Malang City Government not only looks at the effectiveness of the Regional Development Information System, but also needs to look at the effectiveness and efficiency of employees to be able to achieve the main goals of the organization. (Samsuni, 2017).

VI. USING THE TEMPLATE

From the results of the analysis and discussion, it was found that the Regional Development Information System had a significant effect on employee performance. Regional Development Information Systems have a significant influence on organizational effectiveness. Employee performance has a significant effect on organizational effectiveness. Regional Development Information Systems have a significant influence on organizational effectiveness through employee performance.

In this research, it was found that the Regional Development Information System had a direct influence on employee performance, this indicates that the Regional Development Information System within the Malang City government had a direct influence on improving the performance of Malang City government employees. The benefits of this Regional Development Information System also need to be supported by system quality and information quality (Alvianna, Hidayatullah, Windhyastiti, & Khourouh, 2022), Apart from the system, you also need to pay attention to the services provided, at least providing services with excellent service quality (Criswandari, Astuti, & Alvianna, 2021). This Regional Development Information System will assist employees in carrying out their work so that it will have an impact on improving the performance of Malang City government employees. Apart from that, the Regional Development Information System has a direct influence on organizational effectiveness, this indicates that the Regional Development Information System in the Malang City government environment has provided convenience for government employees which has an impact on increasing

the effectiveness of government organizations in Malang City, by so existing work becomes easier and government organizations become more effective with this information system. Employee performance can be seen from the employee's work-life

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